

UNIFICATION OF CIVIL LAW REGULATION OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF LAW ENFORCEMENT

Achilova Liliya Ilhomovna

Acting Professor of the Department of Business Law
of Tashkent State University of Law,

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Law

E-mail: liliya.achilova@mail.ru

ORCID: 0000-0003-0111-0546

Abstract

The article examines current trends and challenges in improving the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of digital transformation. The focus is placed on the need for systematic unification and harmonization of national civil law norms with international standards, as well as on adapting the legislation to the requirements of the digital civil turnover. Special attention is given to the implementation of universally recognized principles of international law and the role of the Hague Conference on Private International Law in the process of legal convergence. The study highlights the importance of Uzbekistan's participation in international initiatives aimed at developing legal mechanisms for regulating the digital economy, electronic commerce, and cross-border private law relations. It is emphasized that the modernization of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan should take into account both internal economic and legal realities and the country's international obligations, including those arising from its accession to the World Trade Organization.

Keywords:

civil legislation, unification of law, digital civil turnover, private international law, Hague Conference, harmonization, World Trade Organization, legal reform, law enforcement, Republic of Uzbekistan.

Ачилова Лилия Илхомовна,

и.о. профессор кафедры Бизнес право Ташкентского
Государственного юридического университета,
доктор философии по юридическим наукам

УНИФИКАЦИЯ ГРАЖДАНСКО-ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИХ УСЛУГ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ПРАВОПРИМЕНЕНИЯ

Аннотация

В статье рассматриваются современные тенденции и проблемы совершенствования гражданского законодательства Республики Узбекистан в условиях цифровой трансформации. Акцент сделан на необходимости системной унификации и гармонизации национальных гражданско-правовых норм с международными стандартами, а также адаптации законодательства к требованиям цифрового гражданского оборота. Особое внимание уделено вопросам имплементации общепризнанных принципов международного права и роли Гаагской конференции по международному частному праву в процессе сближения правовых систем. Отмечается значимость участия Узбекистана в международных инициативах, направленных на развитие правовых механизмов регулирования цифровой экономики, электронной коммерции и трансграничных частноправовых отношений. Подчеркивается, что обновление Гражданского кодекса Республики Узбекистан должно учитывать как внутренние экономико-правовые реалии, так и международные обязательства страны, в том числе в контексте присоединения к Всемирной торговой организации.

Ключевые слова: гражданское законодательство, унификация права, цифровой гражданский оборот, международное частное право, Гаагская конференция, гармонизация, Всемирная торговая организация, правовая реформа, правоприменение, Республика Узбекистан.

Research Relevance

At present, active legislative work is being undertaken to improve the civil legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the objective needs of the digital civil turnover. The international and constitutional-legal characterization of the application of universally recognized principles of international law and the norms of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides an opportunity for a comprehensive and in-depth analysis of all institutions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CC RUz) and for the development of well-grounded, problem-oriented conclusions and proposals for its modernization in light of new legislative objectives in this field.

According to Article 33 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “The State shall create conditions for ensuring access to the global information network, the Internet.” In accordance with the Presidential Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2019, No. R-5464 “On Measures to Improve the Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan,”[1] the current version of the Civil Code does not fully meet the requirements of rapidly evolving economic relations within the country, nor does it correspond to international civil law standards. In particular:

First, the Civil Code retains outdated legal institutions and organizational-legal forms of legal entities that no longer exist in the legal systems of developed market economies.

Second, the Code lacks classical civil law institutions such as “commercial risk,” “equality of business entities,” “fair compensation,” and “refusal to perform contractual obligations.”

Third, it does not regulate several forms of civil contracts and legal relations that are in high demand in the modern market environment, including public-private partnership agreements, dealership contracts, shared construction, cluster production, electronic commerce, cryptocurrency circulation, land privatization, and others.

Fourth, the excessive number of blanket and reference norms (approximately 80) prevents the Code from functioning as a self-executing legal act and diminishes its authority in the regulation of civil relations.

Fifth, the Civil Code provides for an unjustifiably large number of organizational-legal forms of legal entities that are similar in nature and represent a hybrid of norms borrowed from other legal forms (for example, private enterprises and unitary enterprises, which cannot attract investment since the law does not provide for the participation of additional members in their structure).

Sixth, the Code contains public law provisions that do not belong to civil law institutions and includes an excessive number of restrictions concerning private property and contractual relations.

Seventh, the Civil Code is almost entirely devoid of provisions governing the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in civil law relations.

This analysis underscores the necessity for systemic reform and digital modernization of the civil legislation of Uzbekistan, ensuring its harmonization with international legal standards and the realities of the digital economy.

International Private Law Benchmarks for the Improvement of Civil Legislation

The Preamble of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan declares that “this Constitution is adopted on the basis of universally recognized principles and norms of international law.” According to Article 15 of the Constitution, the Republic of Uzbekistan recognizes the unconditional supremacy of the Constitution and laws. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan possesses the highest legal force, has direct effect, and forms the foundation of a unified legal system throughout the entire territory of the country.

International treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with universally recognized principles and norms of international law, constitute an integral part of the national legal system. Where an international treaty of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes rules differing from those provided by domestic law, the rules of the international treaty shall prevail.

In accordance with the Presidential Decree “On Measures to Improve the Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan,” one of the main priority directions in the further modernization of civil legislation is the systematization and unification of civil law norms, ensuring their harmonization with best foreign practices, as well as the implementation of advanced international standards in this field.

In the process of convergence of private international law norms among various states, the terms “unification,” “uniformization,” and “harmonization” are widely used. These concepts reflect the global legal trend toward creating consistent and coherent civil law frameworks, enabling effective cross-border cooperation, legal predictability, and the integration of national systems into the evolving international legal order [2]. International organizations play an important role in the process of unifying international legal acts [3]. The oldest organization in the field of unification of private international law is the Hague Conference on Private International Law (began its work in 1893). The members of this organization include more than 60 countries, including Uzbekistan. As is known, on March 4, 2020, Uzbekistan joined the Hague Conference on Private International Law. Uzbekistan's membership in the Hague Conference will ensure the country's participation in the procedure of unifying the norms of international family and private law, further development of the legal system taking into account world standards, and enhancing the effectiveness of protecting the rights and interests of the country's citizens abroad [4].

Therefore, on September 6-8, 2000, the UN Millennium Declaration was adopted and global development priorities were defined. This document consists of 17 goals and 169 targets, and also defines tasks to increase production in economic sectors through accelerating technical modernization, value-added industries, and information and communication technologies [5].

As is known, the agreement on information technology was adopted at the first ministerial conference of WTO member states (Singapore, 1996) [6]. It defines the principles of international trade in information technologies, providing for the gradual reduction of customs tariffs on information technology products and their elimination (zero tariffs) starting from January 1, 2000. Currently, the World Trade Organization (WTO) is discussing the expansion of the range of goods classified as information technology products. Approximately 40 countries are parties to this Agreement; however, the tariff preferences established under it also extend to other countries.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-214 of December 25, 2023, a strategic task has been set to adapt national legislation and law enforcement practices to the rules, norms, and agreements of the WTO, to complete market access negotiations with at least ten foreign countries annually, and to systematically conduct accession negotiations aimed at the effective completion of Uzbekistan's WTO membership process and entry into the markets of WTO member states.

By its civil-law nature, the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement) is an international treaty that forms part of the package of documents establishing the World Trade Organization (WTO). The Agreement sets minimum standards for the recognition and protection of key objects of intellectual property rights. It was adopted during the Uruguay Round of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade (GATT) in 1994.

The TRIPS Agreement enables the use of highly effective dispute resolution mechanisms available within the WTO framework, as applied to intellectual property. These mechanisms include the possibility of retaliatory measures. For example, if a violation of the copyright of an author from one country occurs in another, the injured country—having gone through the WTO dispute settlement procedures—may impose higher tariffs on the import of certain goods from the offending country.

Primarily, the TRIPS Agreement requires member states to implement all essential provisions of the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, except for those concerning moral rights. In addition, TRIPS introduces a number of new provisions related to the international protection of copyright. The absence of moral rights in the Agreement is justified, as its main focus is on regulating the trade-related aspects of intellectual property. The TRIPS Agreement thus incorporates several fundamental elements that complement the provisions of the Berne Convention [7]. In accordance with these provisions, copyright protection extends to computer programs, the term of protection is lengthened, and international trade in computer programs and other intellectual property objects is restricted with countries that lack the capacity to ensure adequate copyright protection. The Agreement also establishes the requirement for member states to adopt various administrative mechanisms for the protection of copyright. [8].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 15, 2024, No. 908, «On Amendments and Additions to Certain Legislative Acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan Aimed at Bringing the National Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan into Conformity with the Agreements of the World Trade Organization,» represents one of the key measures to accelerate the process of Uzbekistan’s accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO) [9]». One of the primary conditions for accession to the WTO is the harmonization of national legislation with the standards and provisions set forth in the WTO agreements.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Trademarks and Appellations of Origin” has been amended and supplemented to establish a precise procedure for the use of industrial property objects without the consent of the right holder, taking into account the interests of intellectual property owners, and to eliminate the statute of limitations for the protection of rights in cases of unfair use of trademarks by other parties following registration. In accordance with the requirements of the WTO Agreements, amendments have also been introduced to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On

Medicines and Pharmaceutical Activities”, providing for the introduction of procedures to protect the rights of data owners obtained prior to and as a result of clinical trials within the framework of pharmaceutical activities.

Moreover, this Law introduces amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On State Duties”, aimed at unifying patent fees as well as state duties charged for the registration of enterprises with foreign investment and other business entities.

Amendments to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Advertising” are directed toward ensuring equal conditions for domestic and foreign manufacturers.

This Law will contribute to the protection of the rights of industrial property owners, the unification of patent and registration fees, and the harmonization of national legislation with the rules and standards of the World Trade Organization.

Most importantly, international private law instruments serve as a guideline for the unification and systematization of national legislation. Therefore, in the ongoing process of reforming the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, it is essential to take into account the fundamental legal principles and standards established by these international and regional organizations in the field of unification of international private law and the regulation of civil-law relations.[10] In this regard, in the process of reforming the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to take into account the fundamental legal principles and norms of the aforementioned international and regional organizations in the field of unification of international private law regulation of civil law relations.

Research Results in the Context of the Reform and Improvement of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The exercise of civil-law subjective digital rights refers to the actions of subjects of civil-law relations, carried out in accordance with constitutional and legislative norms through the use of information and communication technologies within the digital environment.

The protection of subjective civil digital rights implies a set of legal and technological protection mechanisms employed by both non-judicial (extrajudicial) and judicial entities—including digital courts, the technology of artificial judicial intelligence (AI), and actors of online digital dispute resolution—aimed at preventing, suppressing, restoring, or compensating for the violation of subjective civil digital rights in the digital sphere.

In this civilistic context, the system of civil-law and information-communication technological instruments designed to protect subjective digital rights constitutes a mechanism of smart regulation. This mechanism seeks to ensure the effective realization of the protective function of law within the Internet environment, promoting good faith and reasonableness in the protection of the rights and interests of participants in the digital civil turnover.

Based on this, and taking into account the experience of foreign countries, it is

necessary to supplement the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the following content:

It is proposed to amend Article 111 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

Article 111. Protection of the Rights of Entrepreneurs and Consumers

Entrepreneurship is defined as the independent and initiative-based activity of individuals and legal entities aimed at generating net income through the use of property, production, sale of goods, performance of work, or provision of services, carried out on the basis of the right of private ownership (private entrepreneurship) or on the right of economic management or operational administration of a state enterprise (state entrepreneurship). Entrepreneurial activity is conducted on behalf of, at the risk of, and under the property liability of the entrepreneur.

The State guarantees the freedom of entrepreneurial activity and ensures its protection and support.

The rights of entrepreneurs engaged in activities not prohibited by law are protected through the following means:

1. The ability to carry out entrepreneurial activity without obtaining any permits or submitting notifications, except for those permits and notifications expressly required by legislation;

2. The establishment of a simplified, single-window registration procedure for all types of entrepreneurial activity across all sectors of the economy in one registering authority;

3. The limitation, by legislative acts, of inspections of entrepreneurial activities conducted by state authorities;

4. The compulsory termination of entrepreneurial activity only by court decision and only on grounds established by legislative acts;

5. The establishment, by legislative acts, of lists of types of work, goods, and services that are prohibited for private entrepreneurship, or that are restricted for export or import;

6. The imposition of property liability, as established by law, on state bodies, officials, as well as other persons and organizations, for unlawful interference with entrepreneurial activity;

7. The prohibition for executive, control, and supervisory bodies from entering into contractual relations with business entities regarding the performance of duties that fall within the functions of these bodies;

8. Other means provided for by law.

The establishment of a permitting or notification-based procedure shall be determined by legislation, depending on the level of risk associated with the activity or operation, in order to protect human life and health, the environment, property, national security, and public order.

A permitting procedure shall be established in cases where the requirements set forth by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding products, as well as the requirements for mandatory conformity certification, are insufficient to achieve the objectives of state regulation.

Commercial (entrepreneurial) secrecy is protected by law. The procedure for determining information constituting a commercial secret, the means of its protection, and the list of information that shall not be considered a commercial secret are established by legislation.

The protection of consumer rights shall be ensured by the means provided for in this Code or other legislative acts. Each consumer shall have, in particular, the right to:

- freely conclude contracts for the purchase of goods, and the use of works and services;
- proper quality and safety of goods (works, services);
- complete and reliable information about goods (works, services);
- join public consumer organizations.

It is proposed to amend Article 112 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

Article 112. Prohibition of the Abuse of Entrepreneurial Freedom

Monopolistic and any other activities aimed at restricting or eliminating lawful competition, obtaining unjustified advantages, or infringing upon the rights and legitimate interests of consumers shall not be permitted.

Except in cases provided for by legislative acts, entrepreneurs shall not use civil rights for the purpose of restricting competition, including:

Abuse of a dominant position in the market by entrepreneurs, in particular by limiting or ceasing production, or by withdrawing goods from circulation in order to create shortages or raise prices;

Conclusion and performance of agreements by persons engaged in similar entrepreneurial activities concerning prices, market division, elimination of other entrepreneurs, or other conditions that substantially restrict competition;

Engaging in unfair actions that infringe upon the legitimate interests of another person engaged in similar entrepreneurial activity or consumers (unfair competition), in particular by misleading consumers as to the manufacturer, purpose, method and place of manufacture, quality, or other characteristics of another entrepreneur's goods; by making incorrect comparisons of goods in advertising or other information; by copying the external design of another's goods; and by other means.

Measures to combat unfair competition shall be established by legislative acts.

3. It is proposed to amend Article 24 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to read as follows:

Article 24. Place of Residence of a Citizen Registered in the Digital Register as an Entrepreneur or Engaged in Activities Using Digital Platforms

A citizen shall have the right to engage in such activities at their place of residence or through the use of digital platforms from the moment of registration in the state digital register as an individual entrepreneur.

The provisions of this Code shall apply to the entrepreneurial activities of citizens conducted without the establishment of a legal entity, either at their place of residence (legal address) or through the use of digital platforms, unless otherwise provided by law or arises from the nature of legal relations.

A citizen who violates the requirements of the first part of this Article by engaging in entrepreneurial activity without forming a legal entity, whether on their own land or through the use of digital platforms, shall not have the right to claim that they are not an entrepreneur in electronic transactions or smart contracts. The court may apply the provisions of this Code relating to obligations connected with the conduct of entrepreneurial activity on the land of their residence or through digital platforms to such transactions.

Unless otherwise provided by law, the provisions of this Code shall apply to the entrepreneurial activities of citizens carried out using digital platforms.

4. Digitalization will give a powerful impetus to the development of electronic contractual transactions [11]. In the context of the digital transformation of civil transactions, the social and official role of contracts is increasing. Digital integration unites the legislation of countries with different legal systems [12] Therefore, the integration of the Civil Code norms with those of the European Union and the Eurasian legal family is considered an objective process. Especially in the economy, the development of traditional approaches to optimizing the "uniform rules of the game" is the only reasonable way to forecast the development of the Civil Code. In our country, there is a tendency to incorporate certain elements of European contract law into the draft Civil Code. Considering the European Civil Code and the trends in the codification of European private law, harmonization with the Civil Code norms is required in the Republic of Uzbekistan [13]. One of the important problems from a systemic perspective in the current Civil Code is the lack of legal regulation of electronic transactions as an integral part of the law of obligations. [14] The development of information technologies requires special and detailed legal regulation of electronic transactions in the Civil Code, with the following important components: 1. identification of the person (electronic signature, etc.), 2. recording of the transaction (databases, storage media, etc.), 3. reproduction of the transaction (objective expression). Such practices exist in many developed countries of the Romano-Germanic legal system.

In addition, the Civil Code should establish norms stating that if a contract is concluded in two or more languages, which are considered equally authentic, it is presumed that the words and phrases used in each text have the same meaning. If the words and phrases in each text contradict each other, their interpretation should be

carried out in accordance with the relevant articles, the nature and purpose of the contract, as well as the principle of good faith, etc. Similar norms are contained in Article 466 of the Civil Code of the People's Republic of China.

According to the Concept for Improving Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2019, No. P-5464, measures have been defined for the effective regulation of the use of information and communication technologies in contractual relations [15].

5. Depending on the conditions for implementing projects in a given country, various definitions and classifications of public-private partnership (PPP) forms have been adopted. An analysis of these definitions and forms has shown that a PPP is a mutually beneficial and long-term cooperation between the public and private sectors, which ensures the provision of public services.

The implementation of a PPP is carried out on the basis of the shared interests of the public and private sectors, formalized through a long-term contract that provides for the division of responsibilities and risks among the partnership participants. In international practice, various forms of partnership are used, including concessions, supply contracts (performance of work), leases, production-sharing agreements, and joint ventures [16]. According to the Concept for the Improvement of Civil Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2019, No. P-5464, one of the gaps in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the public-private partnership (PPP) agreement.

In different countries, their own specific legal traditions for structuring cooperation between the public and private sectors have developed and continue to evolve, aimed at addressing the objectives of socio-economic policy. The specific legal mechanisms that allow for the most effective use of PPPs may vary depending on national legal systems and other particularities.

The implementation of PPP agreements in the Republic of Uzbekistan, in our view, is possible on the basis of existing legislation, but with certain particularities taken into account. When budgetary funds are involved in a PPP, it becomes necessary to conclude the agreement exclusively using a competitive procedure, i.e., practically by analogy with public procurement and concessions.

Contracts for the use of state or municipal assets, which constitute so-called public-law property of the state and other public-law entities, are considered, in foreign countries, not civil but public in Germany or administrative in France.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the definition and content of the concept of a public-private partnership may reasonably incorporate elements of civil-law contracts involving the state, as well as other forms of interaction between public and private partners.

In this civil-law framework, it should be noted that a socially oriented model can be equated with the concept of a social state, which, in turn, is directly related to social partnership.

6. The specifics of conducting Islamic insurance, the formation, accounting, use, and distribution of the Islamic insurance fund, the legal status of insurers providing Islamic insurance, and the conditions of their activities are determined in accordance with this Code and the legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan on insurance and insurance activities. Chapter 34-1 of the Civil Code of Kyrgyzstan is dedicated to «Transactions and Contracts in accordance with Islamic Financing Principles [17]».

7. At the same time, it should be noted that the legal relations arising in the organization of social partnership indicate that a partnership agreement has a complex and multifaceted nature. For this reason, it may contain elements of other contracts provided for by law, as well as terms of contracts not explicitly regulated by legislation. Practically, such an agreement cannot consist of a single document adopted at one time; it includes a significant number of documents (appendices, protocols, supplementary agreements, etc.) signed progressively during the execution of the agreement.

Due to the special nature of a social partnership agreement, it is recommended for the legal formalization of the partnership to:

1. Develop a detailed prospective cooperation plan that would serve as the conceptual basis for contractual relations;

2. Coordinate the plan with interested organizations, local self-government bodies, and representatives of civil society;

3. Draft a general framework agreement and separate supplementary agreements in accordance with the accepted legal practice for structuring contracts;

4. Include in the framework agreement references to existing and potential future supplementary agreements and other contractual documents;

5. Sign the general framework social partnership agreement, incorporating the main provisions of the cooperation plan in legal terms, i.e., translating planned activities into the rights and obligations of the parties with specification of the conditions, procedures, and deadlines for their fulfillment.[18] (In a separate article, the Civil Code should be supplemented with the following provisions: Social Partnership Agreement. The subjects of social partnership may enter into agreements and contracts, as well as develop and implement joint projects and plans. Agreements constitute the mutual assumption of obligations by the parties, within which the parties determine the goals and objectives, directions of joint activities, and indicate the forms of implementing social partnership. Contracts may provide for the performance of work or the provision of services, as well as the implementation of socially and publicly significant projects with material, including financial, support from a social partnership subject. Joint

projects and plans define a set of measures aimed at implementing agreements and contracts, socio-economic development programs, addressing humanitarian issues, and protecting the rights, freedoms, and lawful interests of various segments of the population. This provision is contained in Article 10 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Social Partnership” dated September 25, 2014, No. ZRU-376.)

8. Based on this argument, the draft Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was supplemented with Article 453: Smart Contract. A smart contract is defined as a contract in which at least one of the parties is not a human, whose creation and execution are fully automated, based on pre-designed software and algorithms that evaluate, using artificial intelligence, actions and intellectual property rights sufficient for the author to be considered as having achieved their objectives, and which create intellectual property rights alongside contractual relationships with its creator, representing an electronic contract. [19]

As we see it, this definition does not fully capture the nature of a smart contract. In this regard, it is necessary to remove Article 453 from the draft Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. While this provision meets the current requirements of digital civil circulation, its inclusion in the Civil Code at this stage is premature.

It should be particularly noted that Part 2 of Article 117, which establishes the written form of a transaction in the discussed draft, also provides an additional basis for recognizing a digital form of such an unusual and previously unknown civil-law contract.

If necessary, in the further digitalization of civil circulation, a separate chapter can be introduced dedicated to the new constructs of smart contracts as an important element of contractual obligations in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Thus, it can be concluded that the unification of international private and comparative legal regulation of civil relations in the process of reforming the Civil Code of Uzbekistan will make it possible to more effectively and intelligently regulate legal relations in the context of digital civil circulation.

List of references:

1. National Legislation Database, 06.04.2019, No. 08/19/5464/2891

2. chrome

extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://12aas.arbitr.ru/storage/materials/doc2.pdf.

3. Active international organizations engaged in regulatory activities in the field of electronic commerce include the International Chamber of Commerce (ICC), the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL), the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), the World Trade Organization (WTO), as well as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). All these

organizations make a significant contribution to the process of unifying international trade legislation in the online environment. In the context of Uzbekistan's cooperation with the World Trade Organization, one of the most pressing issues is the civil-law protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities operating in the digital economy.

4. <https://uzdaily.uz/ru/post/49916>

5. chrome-

extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgglefindmkaj/http://www.ifapcom.ru/files/2-Deklaratsiya_tysyacheletiya_OON.pdf

6. The Information Technology Agreement (ITA) is a multilateral agreement implemented by the World Trade Organization (WTO) and concluded at the WTO Ministerial Conference in Singapore in 1996. The agreement was set out in the Ministerial Declaration on Trade in Information Technology Products, published during the conference, and entered into force on July 1, 1997.

The declaration emphasizes the “key role of trade in information technology products in the development of information industries and in the dynamic expansion of the global economy.” Since 1997, an official committee under the WTO has monitored the implementation and compliance of the Declaration. The primary objective of the agreement is the reduction of all taxes and tariffs on information technology products by the signatory parties to zero. The agreement was expanded at the WTO Ministerial Conference in Nairobi in 2015. https://translated.turbopages.org/proxy_u/en-ru.ru.ef8bc6ab-665ac3ea-88e5e259-74722d776562/https/en.

7. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%A1%B8>.

8. Мэґс П. Б., Сергеев А. П. Интеллектуальная собственность / Пер. с англ. Л. А. Нежинской. — М.: Юрист, 2000. — 396 с. — ISBN 5797503336.

9. National Legislation Database, 15.02.2024 г., № 03/24/908/0126

10. Xayitmurodov, U. B., & Achilova, L. (2022). Factors of development of islamic financial institutions in modern conditions.

11. Digital in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan: forecasts and current data – <https://www.byyd.me/ru/blog/2024/03/digital-in-kazakhstan-and-uzbekistan/>

12. CARES Institute. Analytical Note. Development of E-Commerce in CARES. April 2021, p.16

13. Kuznetsova I.A., Matveeva T.P., Kuznetsova N.A. Foreign Experience in Regulating Electronic Contractual Obligations by Business Entities – <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zarubezhnyy-opyt-regulirovaniya-elektronno-dogovornyh-obyazatelstv-subektami-predprinimatelskoy-deyatelnosti/viewer>

14. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Commerce”, National Database of Legislation, 30.09.2022, No. 03/22/792/0870

15. Civil Code of China https://chinalawinfo.ru/procedural_law/law_civil_procedure

16. <https://inter-legal.ru/formy-gosudarstvenno-chastnogo-partnerstva-v-zarubezhnyh-stranah>

17. <https://www.menobr.ru/article/4835-kak-pravilno-sostavit-dogovor-o-sotsialnom-partnerstve>

18. Appendix 1 to Decree No. 8 of the Republic of Belarus dated December 21, 2017, “On the Development of the Digital Economy” defines a smart contract as a program code intended to operate in a transaction block registry (blockchain) or another distributed information system for the purpose of automated execution and/or performance of transactions or the undertaking of other legally significant actions.

19. Ilxomovna, A. L. (2023). REGULATION OF BUSINESS ACTIVITIES IN THE FIELD OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF REGULATIONS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPLIANCE WITH LEGISLATION. *The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology*, 5(12), 44-51.